

Live Coding Deep Neural Nets

Shawn Lawson
Arizona State University
shawn.a.lawson@asu.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper will describe the concept to completion process of live coding Pix2Pix and StyleGan2 neural nets for the generation of new visuals. The following pages will describe real-time live coding neural net input data and live coding neural net tensor weights.

1 Introduction

Neural nets (NN) and machine learning (ML) have been newly introduced to the audio arena of live-coding: MIMIC (Grierson et al., n.d.), SEMA (Magnusson, Bernardo, and Kiefer, n.d.), and live-coding agents (Stewart and Lawson 2019; Stewart et al. 2020). To date, there exists less work on integration of ML with live-coded visuals. Machine learning does have a history of being used to generate images: Inceptionism (Mordivtsev, Olah, and Tyka 2015), Learning to See (Akten 2017), Neural Zoom (Crespo, n.d.), Prometheus (Stewart 2020), Edmond De Belamy (Oblivious 2018), or random explorations (Friesen, n.d.). Atken's and Stewart's research are the closest to live-coding visuals with real-time video camera image input to real-time image output. Software like RunwayML and GoogleColab do provide easier methods for visual artists to create an ML art for non-real-time use. And, Dan Shiffman provides good educational entry level opportunities for ML exploration with ml5js on his *The Coding Train* youtube channel. Although, there are significant technical hurdles to setting up and using NNs and ML, especially for real-time performance application.

2 Machine Learning

Machine learning is the process of training a NN with a dataset; whereby, the end goal is to have a robust NN that has as close as possible deterministic correlation between input and output. For example, every A pushed into a NN should return the exact same A'. If A returns B, then the training has not resolved well enough yet. Furthermore, the NN training is only as robust as it's dataset. When the dataset curator does not consider a diverse enough dataset, then unfortunate or catastrophic output can occur. This discovery is most popularized with Joy Boloumwin's discovery of inadequate face tracking, which led to her creation of the Algorithmic Justice League. While this paper does not directly address issues of representation, equity, or inclusion within data collection or curation; the author acknowledges that data collection and curation are critical steps and a historically under-considered component to ML. Dataset curators don't often reflect on the impact their choices have on their data or longevity of their data. Sensitivities towards data, privacy, and their systemic effects were taken with respect to data used in this paper.

Three trained NNs were explored for the writing of this paper. The first was a self-trained pix2pix (Isola et al. 2016) NN of hand-drawings of the author paired with images from the *Liquid Light* youtube channel (Pavlovsky, n.d.). The second NN was a pre-trained stylegan2 (Karras et al. 2020) NN, Mapdreamer, (Tjukanov 2020) available under the Creative Commons zero (CC0) license. The third was a self-trained stylegan2 NN of images of the author's prior live coded visual performances.

3 Setup

While ML can be completed on CPUs, serious machine learning requires an NVidia graphics card on either linux or Windows operating systems. In this paper, live-coding NNs required an NVidia graphics card for real-time throughput and the windows operating system to run Touch Designer (TD). Most ML is accessed with the python scripting language. The author used pytorch for ease of compatibility with other required python libraries and software, but tensorflow could be equally viable option.

Touch Designer was the glue to connect all parts together. This audiovisual patching-like programming environment has a python scripting interface and provides real-time, iterative control over detailed audio and graphics engine choices. TD has a Script-TOP (python script-able texture operator) node that permits copying from and writing to the node's CUDA image buffer. CuPy, a python CUDA library, was used to slice and wrap the CUDA buffer into torch tensors and back to CUDA with minimal or zero GPU memory latency.

Touch Designer allows users to group sets of nodes together and export toxes. Toxes are self contained nodes that can be saved or loaded easily into any TD project. Engine, a new feature of TD, will load a tox file into a separate thread. This is quite beneficial for tasks that need to run at a faster or slower framerate. One down-side to running tox files in TD engine is the requirement of thread safe memory, which, at the moment, reduces the amount and type of external information flow into/out of engine toxes. In this paper, wrapping up the NN processing in a tox file was very beneficial, with the author's available hardware, RTX 2060, NN processing rate averaged 15-25fps. This was decoupled from TD main framerate set at 60fps. The faster the graphics processing card, then the faster NN processing rate.

There are a few remaining notes to mention. Mapdreamer was created in the tensorflow format and the author converted it to torch using a script from a fork (Shultz, n.d.) of the original stylegan2 ada github repository. Live coding was accomplished in the Atom text editor with the Jensaarai package (Lawson 2018). Python and OpenGL fragment shader language are transmitted to TD over Open Sound Control (OSC) communication on a localhost or remote address.

4 Pix2Pix

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are NNs that have two competing NNs: a generator (artist) and a discriminator (critic). The artist's goal is to convince the critic that they have made a masterpiece. The critic's goal is to determine if the artist's work is or is not a masterpiece. When a GAN trains, the artist learns to make images, and conversely the critic learns to assess the images. Each is trying to learn a little faster than the other. The artist's input is random noise. The critic's input is the artist's image and a dataset of human-approved/curated masterpieces. Based on the critic's decision, both the artist's NN and the critic's NN are updated. This process is repeated ad nauseum.

Pix2Pix extends the GAN to be a Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (CGAN). The conditional is the artist's (generator's) input. Instead of the artist receiving noise, they receive image pairs, for example: a photo of a cat and a line drawing based on the photo of the cat. When the artist receives the cat photo they should produce the cat drawing. Then the critic will determine if the cat drawing is a masterpiece. In this way, the Pix2Pix method can be thought of as an image filter or image translator.

The initial idea was to have the visual performance be hand-drawn live in a method similar to Bob Ostertag and Pierre Hébert. Their performance drawings were cast on the wall with overhead projectors and analog video manipulation. The author's intent was to use the Pix2Pix method to transform the live pencil and paper hand-drawing into another aesthetic form and movement. A primary challenge was encountered. The hand-drawn image used for training must be created in exactly the same way during performance. This means that if performance drawing is made with pencil and paper, then the dataset training image must also be pencil and paper. It was discovered that even slight variations from lighting, shadow, paper color, mark-making, and essentially all real-world concerns have drastically large effects on output images from NNs. Building a dataset implied camera capturing all images as scanning images for the dataset would look too different from live performance images. As such, the pencil-paper idea was abandoned.

The next idea was a live screen capture of drawing with a tablet in Photoshop or other drawing software. This would reduce the need for video image capture, but retain the hand-drawn element. Photoshop has settings to enable itself as a server with remote connections. Touch Designer provides a Photoshop TOP node that connects to the Photoshop server and pulls the image buffer. Unfortunately, this connection only shows updates when a drawn stroke completes. This felt disappointing when strokes popped into existence rather than seeing them emerge in real-time. TD also has a Screen Capture TOP node, which was the solution used to sample the image directly from the screen buffer. While the setup of this method worked, it was quite delicate and difficult to prepare and use. Jumping through brush settings and colors felt quite slow. Moreover, the image didn't move or animate.

Eventually, all hand-drawing techniques were dropped and changed to live-coded pix2pix image input using The Force (Lawson, n.d.). The original implementation of The Force is web-browser based and required a similar screen capture technique. To improve image resolution, data copying efficiency, and overall ease of use, a new implementation of The Force was created within TD and made into a modular tox file for use in any future TD project. This TD version of The Force is nearly identical with the primary differences of utilizing TD's built-in shader strengths and OpenGL 4 capabilities instead of WebGL capabilities; put simply, it's faster and pixel resolution is higher.

In the end, pix2pix felt and looked like pushing images through a filter rather than unique, aesthetic image generation. The system felt over-engineered for the image results. When the input was a camera, animation was either ambient or accidental due to fluctuation in the physical world. The paper itself could be moved within the camera's view, which

Figure 1: Left: GLSL image generated by The Force; Right: image after passing through pix2pix.

appeared a little lack-luster. With screen capture of Photoshop drawings, animation was arbitrary and disconnected to the act and visual movement of drawing. Typically what occurred was an overlapping palette window animation or accidental panning/scrolling of the image within the defined capture space. An attempt at animation was constructed with an animated Noise TOP node between the screen capture and pix2pix NN processing. Lastly, with The Force input, animation was introduced from within the OpenGL shader. This resulted in enhancing the appearance of a filtering process when pushed through the pix2pix NN. The conclusion was that this filtering could simply be re-created in the shader or by other less computationally expensive means than with pix2pix, see figure 1.

One idea worth revisiting from this line of experimentation would be labeling. Pix2pix has been used in a few training scenarios to convert single color fields to full-color photo-like images. The two examples they demonstrate are: *Labels to Street Scene* and *Labels to Facades*. In these scenarios a single color represents something, for example: purple is street, navy blue is car, and yellow is stoplight; or, blue is window, orange is lintel, and dark blue is facade. It might be worth training a new set of labels and using video camera input or The Force input as reduced, flat color for other photo-like output. In this way a mosaic-montage of image references could swim together.

5 StyleGan ADA

StyleGan2 ADA (SG2A) is one of the most recent variations of the StyleGan lineage of NNs (Karras et al. 2020). Stylegan models are trained similarly to pix2pix models, except that the goal is to create a high quality image generation latent space. What makes SG2A significantly different from pix2pix from a users or live coders standpoint is the input. Whereas pix2pix required a full image input, SG2A requires a float array. For example, a SG2A trained at 1024x1024 pixels requires as input a 1x512 float array of values ranging from -1 to 1. This array format lends itself quite nicely to becoming a single column of pixels that can be live-coded. For example *Latent Cartographies* (Lawson and Century 2021), a work in progress by the author, navigates the *Mapdreamer* NN using a noise generator to fill this input buffer. *Latent Cartographies's* latent space navigation was controlled through live coding the noise generator properties and applying frequency analysis from audio input. Figure 2 is a capture of that SG2A input. Each pixel column is one frame. Time progresses from left to right. This sample is 512 columns or frames. The image represents our navigation through the SG2A latent space.

Fiebrink, Akten, and Grierson discuss latent space navigation in their paper, “Deep Meditations: Controlled Navigation of Latent Space” (2020). Their input is also a noise-like image; although their intent is to have control over specific destinations in the latent space they wish to arrive at. They designed their navigation to be deterministic and is conceptually very similar to a set of keyframes with parameterized interpolation between the keyframes.

Looking back at figure 2, we see that the change from left to right is quite minimal. This is intentional. See figure 3 for approximately how much latent space navigation change this represents.

Small changes in this data input have a drastically large impact. Other findings include: the roughness/smoothness of noise having direct impact on navigation speed; the type of noise used whether it was simplex, hermite, or Perlin noise; the size or harmonics of noise; and overall noise output range and negative to positive balance. Because the noise is infinitely continuous, sampling through the noise was an easy method of audio controlled navigation. Sound frequency intensity values were added into an accumulator. As this accumulator increased, the noise sampling position was updated. In this way, sound intensity was able to control the pace of NN navigation. To view a short sample of *Latent Cartographies* visit here, <https://vimeo.com/611923465>

Figure 2: 512 columns/frames of SG2A data input

Figure 3: Roughly equivalent amount of change from figure 2 input columns

6 Live-Coding Tensors

Creating a way to live-code tensors was discovered to be easier than anticipated. Although before diving in, it's best to start with a description of a tensor. Tensors are layers of a NN that hold the weights. Each layer is typically a single or multi-dimensional array of data. For images, this is typically three-dimensional, width * height * RGB, (512 * 512 * 3).

To change any tensor value(s) in the generator I load two copies of generator tensor NN. One that acts like a reference (R) and one that does the generation (G) of the images. Both begin with the same initial trained NN weights. The R model never changes. The G model is updated based on my live-coded modulation of R. For example:

$$G = R * 0.3$$

The G model changes and is used to generate the new images based on 30% values from R. In this simplistic scenario, returning image generation to the initial state we set $G = R$. This provides a non-destructive way of modulating the values of the NN. Initial attempts at directly live coding G without an R resulted in an inability to: hold values, prevent G from quickly reaching zero or maximum float value, and reset start state.

Iterating over the tensors by name proved to be the easiest method of specifying which tensor to modify. Each tensor has a dictionary of key, value pairs. When using the *data* key the value it returns is a NumPy like multi-dimensional

Figure 4: From left to right 6.weight tensors multiplied by -0.5, 0, 0.5 1, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5

array. A last point, when generating images, we don't need to load or use the discriminator network. Only the generator network is required.

6.1 Pix2Pix Tensor Weights

Figure 5: From left to right all bias tensors multiplied by -20, -10, 1, 10, and 20

Pix2pix's fundamental principle is how it transforms the input data through reshaping tensors in a process called U-Net. Below is a small sample of the 81 tensors used in the pix2pix generator network.

```
model.model.0.weight
model.model.1.model.1.weight
model.model.1.model.2.weight
model.model.1.model.2.bias
model.model.1.model.2.running_mean
model.model.1.model.2.running_var
model.model.1.model.2.num_batches_tracked
```

Figure 4 and figure 5 are two examples of tensors live-coded with a range of values modifying them. The first figure is modifying a single specific tensor the second is modifying all tensors named "bias." An interesting artifact of modulating tensor weights was the difference in visual appears when increased versus decreased. Both figures exhibit this property and the aforementioned filtering appearance when modulating the tensor values.

6.2 StyleGan2 Tensor Weights

StyleGan2 Has more layers than Pix2Pix at 138. Below is a brief sample of those tensor layers.

```
synthesis.b32.conv0.weight
synthesis.b32.conv0.noise_strength
synthesis.b32.conv0.bias
synthesis.b32.conv0.affine.weight
synthesis.b32.conv0.affine.bias
synthesis.b32.conv1.weight
synthesis.b32.conv1.noise_strength
synthesis.b32.conv1.bias
synthesis.b32.conv1.affine.weight
synthesis.b32.conv1.affine.bias
synthesis.b32.torgb.weight
synthesis.b32.torgb.bias
```

synthesis.b32.torgb.affine.weight
synthesis.b32.torgb.affine.bias

Figure 6: From left to right, fc7.weight tensor multiplied by -1, 0, 1, 2, and 3

Aesthetically interesting results were quickly found with tensors ending in “weight” and “noise_strength.” SG2A also reshapes the tensors in a method similar to pix2pix. Different levels of weight or noise_strength generated similar effects at expectedly different levels of scale. It was also discovered that differences in scale can require a larger or smaller tensor modification for an effect. For example a fc7.weight would need a change by single digits, where fc4.weight could change by 50 either positive or negative for equivalent significant change.

Figure 7: From left to right b16.conv1.noise_strength tensor multiplied by -50, -5, 1, 5, and 50

A surprising result was the visual impression of a completely different effects using a single tensor. In figure 6 lower values quickly erase the image away, while higher values enhance color and retain some detail. In figure 7, lower values begin to create repetitive patterns and solarize the image, while higher values over-sharpen and push the color hues to extremes.

A final experimentation was created with the SG2A trained on the author’s prior performances. The end result was an unexpected, under-filled latent space. Vast areas of the latent space are devoid of imagery with a few pockets of clustered image activity. With the conceptual topic matter being related to global pandemic induced dystopian fever dream future and primary source material from the 1982 version of *Blade Runner* this result enhanced the NN despair-glitch visuals creating interstitial calm between the moments of surreal modern existence. See figure 8 for sequential time-lapse. An additional layer showing the black and white SG2A input data is composited into the final image output. In the spirit of *show us your screens* this layered image reveals all points of the performance. Video samples of *Deckard 2049* here, <https://vimeo.com/621924842>.

Figure 8: From left to right a time-lapse of Deckard 2049

7 Conclusion

Live coding deep neural nets is a viable possibility in which this paper successfully proves the concept, but barely scratches the surface aesthetically and conceptually. Neural nets provide a new range of explore-able aesthetic op-

portunities open to visual live coding performers. It is acknowledged that the technical and challenges to setting up, training, and working with machine learning and neural nets is still quite high. Furthermore, it is of paramount importance that data curation be thoughtfully considered with critical consideration to any future implications.

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